

Understanding history, historical thinking, and historical consciousness, in learning history: An ex post-facto correlation

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Article Info

Article history:

Received Jan 5, 2022

Revised Oct 26, 2022

Accepted Nov 14, 2022

Keywords:

Historical consciousness

Historical thinking

History learning

Understanding history

ABSTRACT

This study aims to analyze the relationship between historical understanding, historical thinking, towards historical consciousness in learning history. This type of research is ex post-facto with a correlational design. The population is class X high school students in Yogyakarta, with a sample of 177. The side technique uses cluster random sampling. Data collection uses instruments in the form of historical understanding tests, historical thinking tests, and historical consciousness questionnaires. Data analysis was carried out through partial correlation and multiple correlations with a significance level of 0.05, and the prerequisite test analysis used normality, linearity, and multicollinearity tests. The results show that the relationship between historical understanding, historical thinking, and historical consciousness in history learning has a strong and significant correlation. These three components should not be separated from the history learning process so that history learning is more meaningful for its historical values.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The development of the progress of the times in the long journey of human history is a process that cannot be avoided by humans as dynamic creatures, both local and global. This is based on the waning of regional boundaries and spatial meanings [1]. Globalization in the 21st century is a phenomenon that occurs because of the advancement of science and technology, which can fade the boundaries of human life. With the conditions of globalization, it can provide convenience for human life in various ways, but on the other hand, it has a contrasting impact [2].

Globalization will unwittingly give birth to a process of homogenization of human culture. Cultural uniformity will eventually shift the unique and distinctive identities of each nation, this is the same as starting to threaten the existence of the identity of a nation [3], [4]. This situation is now happening to the Indonesian people, the Indonesian people are starting to be led by the swift currents of globalization and it does not feel like the nation's identity is starting to be degraded [5]. One of the parameters is that the Indonesian people seem to have begun to forget their past which has become the distinctive identity of every nation, because no nation in this world has the same past [6]. As a result, today's young generation has been immersed in global culture and neglected local and national culture, so that the pattern of daily life makes style and behavior change with styles outside the Indonesian context [7], [8]; for example, imitating the style of Korean culture (Korean Wave) and the style of Western culture. According to Winarni, Slamet, and Syawaludin [9], this can

certainly threaten the nation's identity which is stated in the values of Pancasila amidst the many emerging foreign ideologies that are not under the Indonesian nation.

The problem now is whether people want to learn from the past or their history, to understand the context of their nation. The symptom of the low awareness of the Indonesian people about their history, explained by Adriaan van Dis [10], "Indonesians in general are less interested in the history of their nation, they are more interested in myth, mysticism and fantasy of nationalism." This explanation is indeed inaccurate, but Adriaan van Dis [10] added "the intellectual ability of Indonesian intellectuals is still very lacking." This statement has many defenses from Indonesian intellectuals, because the symptom of the historical consciousness of the Indonesian nation is more directed to a pragmatism life pattern, which carries a tendency to use values (especially practical and materialist) in their thoughts and actions [11].

Explicitly it may be said, in fact what are the practical uses and advantages of historical consciousness or historical awareness. This question is certainly not wrong, but then it can be answered that it is true that historical consciousness is not promising and will not provide practical and material benefits for humans [12]. However, it must also be realized that it does not mean that history has no use value. History as an experience can certainly encourage the life of the nation in the present and the future.

Historical consciousness or historical awareness is an important part as an effort to build individual consciousness and collective consciousness regarding collective identity that can strengthen national character. Another study [13] explains that the current condition of historical consciousness is very relevant and necessary to strengthen and maintain national identity amid a globalized world culture. Clark [14] stated that today's society is dominated by technological sophistication, so that historical consciousness is needed, because the essence of history is the perspective of time and cultural continuity, to understand the pace of development of the times. In line with Grever and Adriaansen [15] that Historical consciousness is a matter that can be used as a vehicle to balance the pace of development of science and technology which seems to be running wildly, so that development does not always have to be material only but needs spiritual balance. Historical consciousness can play a role in strengthening the moral content of a nation [16].

Historical consciousness is a form of aggression from various shared experiences of a community against reactions to cultural, political, economic, educational, and so on situations at one time to another [17]. Historical consciousness can include such as historical insight, ideas contained in historical insight itself, theoretical and methodological foundations of historical research, and written and oral explanations of history. Historical consciousness has been used as the basis for cultural continuity and national integration [18], [19]. Historical consciousness is not only aimed at equipping students with knowledge of historical facts, but also introducing students to historical ways of thinking, understanding and interpreting history, and interpreting history [20]. Historical consciousness means to understand the nature of historical experience, past, present, and future which are connected to each other to acquire that historical knowledge, so that it is related to the concept of historical understanding and historical thinking.

Historical understanding is the ability to capture the meaning of an understanding that has been studied to consider actions related to past events to make it better for the future. This understanding can be called historical intelligence, or historical thinking. Someone who has historical intelligence will be interpreted as intelligent in understanding his past so that he can take lessons [21], [22]. Understanding history is part of the reconstruction of the past to enrich the horizons of thought because past events certainly contain various sources of information and inspiration as well as inexhaustible material to be studied for the sake of present and future life [23]. Meanwhile, thinking of history as a form of reasoning typical of history, in a creative effort to obtain historical knowledge more accurately by exploring certain historical conditions based on awareness, that life in the past was different from life now.

History learning has a strategic role to develop and hone students' abilities related to historical understanding, historical thinking, and historical consciousness. With history learning, students can be directed to develop historical intelligence to reflect positive values from historical events, so that they become wise in acting [24], [25]. History learning is generally oriented towards meaningful learning for students so that the desired achievement can be achieved optimally.

Understanding history, historical thinking, and historical consciousness are needs for the Indonesian people to be studied in history learning so that they cannot be separated from understanding the history of the Indonesian nation itself. Through understanding history, it can raise awareness that it is history that shapes life in the present and determines life in the future. With an understanding of history, it is possible to develop a pattern of thinking, namely historical thinking through critical, creative, and imaginative thinking patterns. This means with the intelligence of historical thinking, socio-national phenomena can be understood carefully, clearly, and comprehensively, so it emerged the wisdom and historical consciousness. The purpose of this study is to examine the relationship between historical understanding, historical thinking, towards historical consciousness in learning history as a unit to grow the nation's character and play a role in strengthening the moral content of the development of a nation.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

The method used in this study is ex post facto, which aims to find the causes that allow changes in behavior, symptoms, or phenomena caused by an event, or things that cause changes in the independent variables [26]. The research design uses a correlational design, which aims to determine the extent of the relationship between two or more variables [27]. The data collected consists of two variables, namely historical understanding (X_1), historical thinking (X_2), and historical consciousness (Y).

2.1. Population, sample, and sampling technique

The population is 210 students taken from state Senior High School 8 Yogyakarta (SMA N 8) and *Madrassa Aliyah* (Senior High School under Ministry of Religion) 1 Yogyakarta (MAN 1) as presented in Table 1. The sample is 177 class X students. The sampling technique is cluster random sampling where the researchers divide the population into several separate groups (clusters) [28]. The sample calculation uses the Isaac and Michael formula, because the number of samples in this study is unknown and using an error rate of 5% [29]. In determining the number of samples for each school, samples were taken from each school randomly, by drawing the names of students in each school so the required number of samples was obtained. Furthermore, the sample for each class determined using the formula according to Riduwan and Akdon [30].

Table 1. Details of the research sample

School	Class	Population	Determination population	Samples
SMA N 8	X IPA 1	35	$\frac{35}{210} \times 177 = 29.50$	30
	X IPS 1	36	$\frac{36}{210} \times 177 = 30.34$	30
	X IPS 2	34	$\frac{34}{210} \times 177 = 28.65$	29
MAN 1	X IPS 1	35	$\frac{35}{210} \times 177 = 29.50$	30
	X IPS 2	35	$\frac{35}{210} \times 177 = 29.50$	30
	X IPS 3	34	$\frac{34}{210} \times 177 = 28.65$	29
Total		210		177

2.2. Measuring instrument

Data was collected using tests and questionnaires. The test instrument was used to collect data related to historical understanding and historical thinking, while the questionnaire was used to reveal data about historical consciousness attitudes [31]. The test instrument for historical understanding and historical thinking is in the form of multiple-choice with a choice of four answers, namely, a, b, c, and d, which includes understanding, memory, analysis, and evaluation. Respondents are expected to answer from the choices that have been given, for the correct answer is given a score of 1, while the wrong one is given a score of 0. While the questionnaire instrument for historical consciousness uses a Likert scale model with five alternative answers, consisting of positive and negative statements.

2.3. Validity and reliability of measuring instruments

Validity using content and constructs. Content validity is assessed by experts to measure the indicators achieved. Construct validity using the biserial correlation coefficient formula, with the results of the validity of historical understanding obtaining a correlation score of >0.455 , 20 valid questions, and three invalids, obtaining a correlation score of >0.421 , with 20 valid questions, and four invalids, historical consciousness obtaining a correlation score >0.411 with 18 valid and five invalid statements. While reliability uses KR 20, the instrument is said to be reliable if it has a reliability coefficient >0.6 [32]. The results of each historical understanding instrument (X_1), historical thinking (X_2), and historical consciousness (Y) are declared reliable because they have a reliability coefficient >0.6 , so all instruments are reliable and can be continued at the analysis and hypothesis testing stage.

2.4. Data analysis

Data analysis uses parametric statistical methods, which aim to test hypotheses by involving population parameters. Data analysis was carried out with the help of the IBM Statistics SPSS 22 Program, through partial and simultaneous multiple correlation tests to see the relationship between historical understanding (X_1), historical thinking (X_2), and historical consciousness (Y) in history learning. The partial multiple correlation test is used for only two variables, meanwhile, the multiple correlation test was used simultaneously for more than two variables. Before testing the hypothesis, it is necessary to analyze the description and test prerequisites to test whether the data has met the requirements. The prerequisite test consists of normality, linearity, and multicollinearity tests.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Result

3.1.1. Descriptive analysis

The category of each variable by setting categorical criteria assumes that the scores of subjects in the population are normally distributed according to the standard normal curve. The category used is a category that is normally distributed. Based on this, the categorization norm of each variable, namely historical understanding, most respondents obtained the medium category with a total of 70 respondents (51.4%), which was supported by an average value of 9.55. Thinking history with a total of 60 respondents (45.6%), with an average value of 11.3, shows that thinking history is in a good category. Meanwhile, the historical consciousness of 47 respondents (37.9%), with an average value of 9.68, indicates that historical consciousness is in the moderate category.

3.1.2. Prerequisite analysis test

The results of the normality test in Table 2 show that the data variance is normally distributed. Based on the results of the analysis of the normality test using the Shapiro-Wilk model the acquisition value of the historical understanding variable is 0.348, historical thinking is 0.670, historical consciousness is 0.432. So, the acquisition of each variable is greater than 0.05 (significance>0.05).

Table 2. Normality test results

Variable	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk			Description
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.	
Understanding history (X ₁)	066	177	157	979	177	348	Normal
Historical thinking (X ₂)	123	177	568	952	177	670	Normal
Historical consciousness (Y)	128	177	281	933	177	432	Normal

The results of the linearity test in Table 3 show that the historical understanding variable is the value of Sig. Deviation from Linearity got a score of 0.848, and the historical thinking variable got a score of 0.867, which means it is greater than the value >0.05. Then there is a linear relationship between the independent and dependent variables. The results of the multicollinearity test as seen in Table 4 show that the variables of historical understanding and historical thinking have a tolerance value of 0.964 (tolerance>0.10), and a VIF value of 1.037 (VIF<10), which means that there is no multicollinearity.

Table 3. Linearity test results

Variable	F Linearity	Sig.	Criteria	Description
Understanding history (X ₁)	1.821	848	p>0.05	Linear
Historical thinking (X ₂)	2.646	867	p>0.05	Linear

Table 4. Linearity test results

Variable	Tolerance	VIF	Description
Understanding history (X ₁)	964	1.037	There is no multicollinearity
Historical thinking (X ₂)	964	1.037	There is no multicollinearity

3.1.3. Hypothesis testing analysis

The results of the hypothesis test in Table 5 with the help of the IBM Statistics SPSS 22 Program, using a partial correlation show that the relationship between historical understanding and historical consciousness has a partial value of 0.456 with a significance of 0.007 (p<0.05), meaning that there is a positive relationship on historical consciousness. While the relationship between historical thinking and historical consciousness obtained a partial value of 0.321 with a significance of 0.006 (p<0.05). Thus, historical understanding and historical thinking have a significant relationship to historical consciousness.

Table 5. Partial correlation test results

Variable	Partial	Sig.	Criteria	Description
Understanding history (X ₁) towards historical consciousness (Y)	456	007	p<0.05	Significant
Historical thinking (X ₂) towards historical consciousness (Y)	321	006	p<0.05	Significant

The results of the simultaneous multiple correlation test in Table 6 with the help of the IBM Statistics SPSS 22 Program, show that there is a simultaneous correlation between historical understanding, historical thinking, and historical consciousness in history learning. This is based on the acquisition of Sig. F Change of 0.000 which is smaller than 0.05 ($p < 0.005$), and the acquisition of an R-value of 0.732. Thus, historical understanding and historical thought have a significant relationship together with historical consciousness.

Table 6. Simultaneous multiple correlation test results

Variable	R	R Square	Sig. F Change	Criteria	Description
Understanding history and historical thinking toward historical consciousness	732	512	000	$p < 0.05$	Significance

3.2. Discussion

The results of the simultaneous multiple correlation test analysis explain that the correlation between historical understanding, historical thinking, and historical consciousness in history learning has a significant relationship with a strong category. This means that the relationship of the three variables is complementary to be taught in history learning, so that learning is more interesting and has a quality weight. The results of previous studies [33] explained that the understanding of history and historical consciousness has a very close relationship; because historical consciousness cannot be separated from historical understanding [34]. Understanding history refers to the cognitive aspect while historical consciousness is categorized as affective and social aspects. The two can be distinguished but cannot be separated. As stated by Aman [35] that history learning serves to build sociocultural and generate historical consciousness.

Understanding history with historical consciousness is a concept that cannot be separated from history learning because history is able to become a benchmark for acting in life so that historical explanations can provide an overview of life and show important values that should be a measure of action. This means that historical understanding teaches about how to understand changes in life in the past through ideas that have consequences for life in the present and in the future [36]. Understanding history tends to think reflects the positive values of historical events so that they will be wiser in acting and responding to life's problems [37]. An understanding of history provides clues that have a set of educational values for future life.

Historical thinking is a way of thinking that gives students the flexibility to construct and interpret historical events through logical reasoning and thinking. Historical thinking forms the skills acquired from studying history and understanding historical events [38], [39]. Thinking about history cannot be separated from the aspect of understanding history. Because the ideal history learning is not limited to the knowledge aspect only [40], [41]. Students are required to understand the development of historical events imaginatively and analytically.

Historical thinking with historical consciousness is an integral part of learning history as a continuation of the concept of understanding history itself. Previous research [42] provides an understanding that historical thinking is a form of reasoning skill that must be possessed when studying history so that students are not only required to remember historical events but must also be able to develop their thinking skills [43]–[46]. This is what will later become historical consciousness or awareness to gain historical insight or knowledge, to invite students to do history both studying history, reading history, interpreting history, and so on so that history learning will be more optimal and interested in historical values and exemplary [47].

The relationship between historical understanding, historical thinking, and historical consciousness in history learning is a framework that cannot be separated because these three components are very relevant to be studied in history learning to make it more meaningful. In general, understanding history is part of cognition to find out collective experiences or events and take meaning from the past to be used as a guide for life based on a critical perspective. From there, historical thinking patterns will develop and become a historical consciousness of the importance of learning from the past which will become an inseparable part of life. Sung [48] explains that historical consciousness is a mental attitude or mental attitude and a state of mind as strength. Historical consciousness itself includes insight into historical facts and their causal relationships, filling the mind with reasonable logic, and increasing conscience equipped with wisdom in dealing with problems and reflecting on past experiences [49], [50].

Historical consciousness as one of the goals of history learning is an attitude that needs to be developed and exists in every student, to make his mind intact, soul, and taste intact [51]. Therefore, in a society that has historical consciousness, dehumanization will be minimal [52]. Meanwhile, understanding

history and thinking about history will make people understand better what needs to be done and what doesn't, what needs to be considered, and what should be done. Thus, the concept of history learning that always puts forward certain goals will be able to make history learning more meaningful so that it will have the ability to think critically, imaginatively, and inspiringly that can be used to understand and find solutions to contemporary problems.

4. CONCLUSION

The relationship between historical understanding and historical thinking, toward historical consciousness in history learning has a strong and significant correlation based on the results of multiple correlation tests simultaneously. This means that the three components of history learning should not be separated just like that, even though they can be distinguished. The concept of history learning has an achievement, namely an awareness or can be called conscientization which means critical awareness of the existing reality. Conscientization occurs because it is built continuously or simultaneously through a historical learning process that will lead to ongoing and continuous reflection. The theoretical implications can be used as a reference for this research. While practically it can be taken into consideration by the teacher to always teach the three components in this research, so that the history learning process will be much more meaningful in terms of educative values and character.

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